

Preliminary Phytochemical Analysis, *In vitro* Antioxidant, and Antimicrobial Effects of Saponins from *Curcuma neilgherrensis* root

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GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION

Abstract

Background: Phytochemicals, the natural bioactive compounds found in plants, are the key to the medicinal properties of the plants. Medicinal plants have long been recognized for their remarkable salutary effects, providing a wealth of natural compounds with the potential to address various health concerns. **Objective:** The main aim of this work was to assess the phytochemical profile, as well as the antibacterial and in vitro antioxidant properties of the *Curcuma neilgherrensis* root extracts. **Methodology:** The various solvents were used to extract the powdered root of the *C. neilgherrensis*. The total saponins were extracted from the root extract of the *C. neilgherrensis*. The preliminary phytochemical composition was evaluated by standard qualitative methods. The in vitro antioxidant capacity of the total saponins extracted from the *C. neilgherrensis* roots were investigated through the utilization of different analytical methods, such as DPPH scavenging, reducing power, ABTS scavenging, and NO scavenging assays. The antimicrobial capabilities of the total saponins extracted from the *C. neilgherrensis* roots were evaluated using the well diffusion technique. **Results:** The present results proved the occurrence of several phytochemicals such as alkaloids, flavonoids, triterpenoids, carbohydrates, saponins, steroids, tannins, and chromogenic compounds in the aqueous, ethanolic, petroleum ether, and chloroform extracts

of the *C. neilgherrensis*. The present findings are proved that the total saponins extracted from the *C. neilgherrensis* roots are effectively scavenged the numerous free radicals such as DPPH, ABTS, and NO. The results of antimicrobial assay was proved that the various doses of the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* demonstrated remarkable antimicrobial efficacy against all the pathogens tested, similar to the results obtained with standard antibiotic amoxicillin. **Conclusion:** The present investigation proved that the *C. neilgherrensis* root extract has numerous phytochemicals and showed promising antimicrobial and antioxidant effects. Therefore, it was evident that *C. neilgherrensis* has the potential to be advantageous in addressing disorders caused by infection and oxidative stress.

Keywords: Oxidative stress, Infections, *Curcuma neilgherrensis*, Pathogens, Free radicals.

Introduction

Medicinal plants have been an imperative part of human history for millions of years, providing as a primary source of healthcare and livelihood for indigenous and rural populations globally. These plants possess a diverse array of phytochemicals that confer them with remarkable medicinal properties, making them a valuable resource for drug discovery and development [1]. The importance of medicinal plants is well-recognized, with studies indicating that they form the foundation of healthcare for approximately 85% of the world's population. These plants are often considered safe and non-toxic, with a long history of conventional utilization, making them a preferred choice over synthetic drugs, which may be subject to adulteration and carry the risk of side effects [2]. Phytochemicals, the natural compounds found in medicinal plants, are the key to their medicinal power. These bioactive molecules can have a numerous of physiological effects on the human body, acting as antioxidants, anti-inflammatory agents, antimicrobials, and more. Researchers are constantly

exploring and validating the traditional uses of medicinal plants through scientific investigation, aiming to develop novel lead compounds for pharmaceutical applications [3].

Medicinal plants have long been recognized for their remarkable salutary properties, providing a wealth of natural compounds with the potential to address various health concerns. One of the key areas of interest in the scientific community is the exploration of the antimicrobial and antioxidant capabilities of these plants[4]. Various studies have confirmed the antimicrobial effect of various herbal plants, with their phytochemicals playing an essential role in inhibiting the proliferation of pathogenic microorganisms [5,6]. Essential oils derived from aromatic plants, in particular, have demonstrated promising antimicrobial properties, which can be further enhanced when combined with conventional antibiotics. This synergistic approach is especially relevant in the face of growing antimicrobial resistance, as it presents an alternative strategy to overcome the challenges posed by multi-drug resistant strains [7]. In addition to their antimicrobial potential, herbal plants have also garnered significant attention for their antioxidant properties. Natural antioxidants derived from plant sources, such as chemical constituents and raw extracts, have proven to be highly effective in neutralizing free radicals and blocking the process of oxidation [8]. This has important implications for human health, as oxidative stress is associated to numerous diseases.

The assessment of the antioxidant property of medicinal plants is a crucial aspect of this research, as it involves the careful assessment of the extraction methods, as well as the accurate analysis of the antioxidant ability of the plant-derived compounds [9]. The incorporation of these natural antioxidants into various products, such as food and cosmetics, further underscores the importance of understanding the potent health benefits of medicinal plants. *Curcuma neilgherrensis*, a member of the Zingiberaceae family, is commonly known as "Kattukalvazhai" in Tamil. This plant is utilized as a traditional remedy by the tribes residing in the Western Ghats region to treat diabetes. Similarly, the Palliyar tribes in

Tamilnadu consume the tuber for its edible properties. The leaf is regarded as the beneficial component for mitigating the adverse consequences of diabetes [10]. Despite its repute, this plant has not yet undergone scientific investigation, making it worthwhile to conduct a detailed examination of its therapeutic properties. The existing textual knowledge about the herb is extremely limited and insufficient. Therefore, this study examines its phytochemical profile, antioxidant, and antimicrobial properties.

Materials and methods

Collection and authentication of plant material

The root of the *C. neilgherrensis* was harvested from the highest point of Yercaud hills, located in the Salem district, Tamil Nadu. It is accompanied by an authentication certificate with the number GRD/2024/470. Immediately following the collection, the root was subjected to a 15-day shade drying process in order to eliminate any moisture present. The sample is then finely ground into powder using a mechanical blender and filtered using a No.40 sieve. Finally, the powdered plant sample was utilized for the extraction process.

Extraction of the plant material

The extraction of the plant material was performed using a Soxhlet device. The root's coarse powder was initially extracted using petroleum ether. The defatted material was subjected to further extraction using different solvents including chloroform, ethanol, and water. Following the extraction process, the extracts were concentrated using a rotary evaporator and subsequently dried at room temperature to obtain a thick and sticky substance. The crude extracts obtained were weighed and stored at 4°C for the subsequent examination of their antioxidant, antibacterial, and antidiabetic characteristics.

Extraction of saponins

The initial step involved the removal of fat from the powdered material using petroleum ether and n-hexane. The defatted substance was subsequently extracted using methanol. The Ethanolic extract was condensed utilizing vacuum during rotational evaporation. The dried ethanolic extract was dissolved in distilled water and agitated with n-butanol. The resulting liquid was then treated with diethyl ether to precipitate a crude Saponin mixture. A conical flask is filled with 100 g of the sample, and 500 ml of aqueous ethanol was added. The aforementioned solution is heated in a water bath for 4 hours, with constant agitation at a temperature of around 55°C. The suspension is filtered, and the remaining solid is again extracted using 200 ml of ethanol at a concentration of 20%. The mixed extracts are condensed to around 40 ml using a water bath at a temperature of around 90°C. The suspension is poured into a separating funnel with a capacity of 250 ml, and 20 ml of diethyl ether was mixed. The mixture is then forcefully agitated. The water layer is collected while the organic solvent layer is discarded. The procedure of purification is repeated. The n-butanol extracts are added and then washed with 10 ml of sodium chloride. The residual suspension is heated using a water bath. Following evaporation, the sample is subjected to oven drying until it reaches a stable weight, and the saponin content is then determined as a percentage.

Preliminary phytochemical analysis of the *C. neilgherrensis*

Organic and aqueous extracts of *Curcuma neilgherrensis* obtained by the above method was analyzed qualitatively for the occurrence of numerous phytochemicals phenolic groups, glycosides, alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, terpenoids, saponins, oils and gums as described earlier [11-12].

In vitro antioxidant assays

DPPH radical scavenging analysis

The DPPH radical scavenging ability of *C. neilgherrensis* was assessed using the previous method [14]. Various amounts of saponin extracts of *C. neilgherrensis* (0.5 ml each) were combined with a 1-ml methanol containing DPPH (0.1 mM) reagent. The combination was left undisturbed for 30 minutes in the absence of light. The measurement of absorbance was conducted at 523 nm. The standard and blank were prepared using an equimolar quantity of DPPH and methanol, respectively. The scavenging capacity was determined by applying the following equation:

$$\text{DPPH scavenging (\%)} = (A_c - A_s)/A_c \times 100,$$

Where, A_s is the absorbance of the test sample and A_c is the absorbance of the control.

Reducing Power Assay

The Fe³⁺ reduction capacity of the plant extract was assessed using the previous method [15]. The 0.75 mL sample of different dosages were combined with 0.75 mL of saline and 0.75 mL of potassium hexacyanoferrate. The suspension was then heated using water bath at 50°C and incubated for 20 minutes. The reaction was halted by introducing 0.75 mL of a 10% of trichloroacetic acid (TCA), followed by centrifuging the mixture at a force of 800 g for a duration of 10 min. 1.5 milliliters of the collected supernatant was combined with 1.5 milliliters of distilled water and 0.1 ml of FeCl₃ for 10 min. The measurement of the absorbance was conducted at 700 nm. A higher degree of absorbance in the suspension reveals a larger level of reducing power.

Hydroxyl peroxide (H₂O₂) radical scavenging analysis

The H₂O₂ scavenging effect of *C. neilgherrensis* was studied using an earlier technique [16]. The reaction suspension consisted of deoxyribose (2.8 mM), KH₂PO₄-NaOH buffer with a pH of 7.4 (0.05 M), FeCl₃ (0.1 mM), EDTA (0.1 mM), H₂O₂ (1 mM), and various dosages of *C. neilgherrensis* extracts with the 2 ml of total volume of the suspension. The solution was kept at 37°C for 30 min. After that, trichloroacetic acid and thiobarbituric acid were added. Subsequently, it was subjected to a 30-minute incubation in a water bath at boiling temperature, followed by a cooling process. Finally the absorbance was taken at 532 nm.

ABTS scavenging assay

The ABTS scavenging activity of several extracts of *C. neilgherrensis* was assessed using the same method as previously published [17]. Briefly, a solution was prepared by dissolving potassium persulfate (37.5 mg) in distilled water (1 ml). To prepare the ABTS reagent, 44 µl of this suspension was mixed to ABTS (9.7 mg) dissolved in distilled water (2.5 ml). The ABTS reagent was left undisturbed in darkness for approximately 15 h at 37°C. The various concentrations of *C. neilgherrensis* were combined with 250 µl of ABTS and left undisturbed for 4 min. The measurement of absorbance was taken at a wavelength of 734 nm. The outcomes was quantified in terms of rutin equivalent, which served as the reference standard.

Nitric oxide (NO) scavenging assay

The NO scavenging effect was assessed using the previously reported technique [18]. The sodium nitroprusside (5 mM) was combined with various amounts of *C. neilgherrensis* extracts in PBS. The mixture was then incubated at 25°C for 150 min. Next, the extracts were

combined with Griess reagent. The measurement of the absorption by the chromophore produced during the reaction between nitrite and sulfanilamide, followed by the reaction with NED, was taken at 546 nm.

Antimicrobial activity

The antibacterial effectiveness of the *C. neilgherrensis* extract against the various pathogens such as *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Candida albicans*, and *Candida tropicalis* were studied using well diffusion technique. The experiment utilized the corresponding agar growth media for bacteria and fungal cultures, respectively. Following the introduction of pathogens onto their respective plates, wells are developed on the agar surface. The *C. neilgherrensis* at dosages of 25, 50, 75, and 100 mg/mL were then loaded to the wells. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hr. The diameter of the inhibitory zones was observed after a time of incubation.

Results

Results of the phytochemical analysis of the *C. neilgherrensis* extracts

Table 1: Results of the preliminary phytochemical analysis of the *C. neilgherrensis* extracts

S.No	Phytochemicals analyzed	Aqueous	Ethanol	Petroleum ether	Chloroform
1	Alkaloid	++	++	-	-
2	Flavonoid	+++	+++	-	-
3	Triterpenoid	++	+++	+	+
4	Carbohydrates	+	++	-	-

5	Saponin	+++	+++	-	-
6	Steroids	++	+++	+	+
7	Amino acid	-	-	-	-
8	Tannin	++	+++	++	+
9	Gums &Mucilage	-	-	-	-
10	Chlorogenic compound	+	++	-	-

Table 1 illustrates the findings of phytochemical analysis of the numerous solvent extracts of *C. neilgherrensis*. The results proved the occurrence of various secondary metabolites in the aqueous, ethanolic, petroleum ether, and chloroform extracts of the *C.*

neilgherrensis. The occurrence of the numerous phytochemicals like alkaloids, flavonoids, triterpenoids, carbohydrates, saponins, steroids, tannins, and Chlorogenic compounds were evidenced in the various solvent extracts of the *C. neilgherrensis*. When compared with chloroform and petroleum ether solvent extracts, the methanol and aqueous extracts of the *C. neilgherrensis* were demonstrated the occurrence of numerous phytochemicals. Therefore, the ethanolic extract of the *C. neilgherrensis* was utilized for the additional studies.

Separation and purification of total saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* extract

The dehydrated ethanolic extract of *C. neilgherrensis* functioned as an emulsifier by improving the process of emulsification of ethyl-ether in water. The saponins were successfully recovered in a relatively pure form after destabilizing the emulsion. Demulsification was facilitated by phase separation, which occurs as a result of the transition from an oil-in-water (o/w) emulsion to a water-in-oil (w/o) emulsion. The observed separation is characterized by Winsor II phase-equilibrium, where the emulsifier components are fully saturated in the upper organic phase, resulting in a creamy suspension that appears quite turbid. The upper phase exhibited noticeable deposition of particles, which contributed to the increased retrieval of saponins. The purity of the final product was significantly enhanced through three consecutive purification processes, resulting in a notable improvement in its physical appearance. Furthermore, the additional confirmation tests such as foam test, lead acetate test, conc. H₂SO₄ test, formaldehyde, and salkowski tests were performed to further confirm the separation and purification of total saponins (Table 2). The results of these tests were also proved the successful separation of the total saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* (Figure 1).

Table 2: Confirmation tests for the saponins extracted from the *C. neilgherrensis* extract

TESTS	RESULTS
Foam Test	+++
Lead Acetate Test	+++
Conc. H₂SO₄ Test	+++
Formaldehyde & Conc. H₂SO₄ Test	+++
Salkowski Test	+++

Figure 1: Separation and purification of total saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* extract

1. Collection of *Curcuma neilgherrensis* 2. Drying of *Curcuma neilgherrensis* root 3. Powder of *Curcuma neilgherrensis* root 4. Defatting 5. Soxhlet extraction with non-polar solvent (Petroleum ether). 6. Concentration under reduced pressure 7. Partitioning with separating funnel (1:1 water –n- butanol) 8. Collection of n- Butanol fraction 9. Concentration under reduced pressure 10-12 Evaporation for dryness 13-14. Confirmation analysis

Effect of saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* on the DPPH scavenging

The DPPH radical scavenging effects of saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* was measured, and the findings are compared with rutin. The DPPH radical scavenging potential of saponin from *C. neilgherrensis* was displayed in Figure 2. The saponin from *C. neilgherrensis* was measured at diverse dosages (20-100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), resulting in inhibition percentages of 30.06 ± 1.16 , 49.03 ± 3.54 , 67.54 ± 2.64 , 82.55 ± 2.62 , and 94.42 ± 1.93 , respectively. Similarly, the inhibitory effect of standard drug rutin was measured at dosages of 20, 40, 60, 7, and 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, resulting in inhibition percentages of 39.13 ± 2.98 , 59.42 ± 2.12 , 68.76 ± 3.14 , 88.67 ± 2.22 , and 95.86 ± 2.43 , respectively. The IC₅₀ values for the DPPH scavenging potential of saponin from *C. neilgherrensis* and rutin were determined to be 44 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 18 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively. *C. neilgherrensis* exhibited a dose-dependent elevation in inhibitory effects (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Effect of saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* on the DPPH scavenging assay

The findings were depicted as a mean \pm SD of three independent assays. The results are statistically assessed by one-way ANOVA and Tukey's post hoc assay using SPSS software.

Effect of saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* on the H₂O₂ radical scavenging assay

The activity of saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* on scavenging H₂O₂ was detected and, and the findings are compared with standard drug rutin. The figure 3 represents the H₂O₂ scavenging activity of saponins derived from *C. neilgherrensis* and rutin. The inhibitory effect of saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* was assessed at diverse dosages (20-100 µg/ml) and the inhibition was observed to be 26.38±3.0, 36.18±2.84, 44.37±1.75, 60.75±3.34, and 77.24±1.78, respectively. In contrast, the inhibitory effect of rutin at the same dosages was found to be 86.62±2.24, 65.53±1.92, 58.66±2.96, 38.87±2.51, and 28.90±2.38, respectively. The IC₅₀ level for the scavenging effect of H₂O₂ by saponins from *C. neilgherrensis* and rutin were 61.33 µg/ml and 51.39 µg/ml, respectively. *C. neilgherrensis* exhibited a dose-dependent elevation in inhibitory effect (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Effect of saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* on the H₂O₂ radical scavenging assay

The findings were depicted as a mean ± SD of three independent assays. The results are statistically assessed by one-way ANOVA and Tukey's post hoc assay using SPSS software.

Effect of saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* on the NO radical scavenging assay

The NO radical scavenging effects of the saponins extracted from *C. neilgherrensis* was quantified and the findings are compared with rutin. The NO radical scavenging potential of saponins from *C. neilgherrensis* was presented in Figure 4. The inhibitory property of saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* on NO was measured at numerous dosages (20-100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). The observed percentages of NO inhibition were 20.32 ± 1.53 , 29.99 ± 1.81 , 40.20 ± 2.61 , 53.81 ± 2.29 , and 71.73 ± 2.52 , respectively. The percentage inhibition of rutin at same dosages were determined to be 21.30 ± 1.98 , 34.77 ± 1.80 , 49.58 ± 2.35 , 66.3 ± 2.66 , and 81.29 ± 2.29 , respectively (Figure 4). The IC₅₀ level for the NO scavenging potential of saponin extracted from *C. neilgherrensis* and rutin were determined to be $69.66 \mu\text{g/ml}$ and $59.30 \mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively.

Figure 4: Effect of saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* on the NO radical scavenging assay

The findings were depicted as a mean \pm SD of three independent assays. The results are statistically assessed by one-way ANOVA and Tukey's post hoc assay using SPSS software.

Effect of saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* on the ABTS radical scavenging assay

The ABTS scavenging effects of saponins derived from *C. neilgherrensis* on ABTS radical was measured and the findings are compared to the standard drug rutin. Figure 5 depict the results of saponins from *C. neilgherrensis* and rutin to scavenge H₂O₂. The inhibitory effects of diverse dosages (20-100 μ g/ml) of saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* on ABTS radical was observed to be 32.57 ± 2.99 , 50.07 ± 2.54 , 61.73 ± 2.82 , 77.82 ± 2.76 , and 89.36 ± 2.50 , respectively. Similarly, the inhibitory effects of rutin at same dosages were found to be 40.21 ± 2.99 , 45.84 ± 2.54 , 68.62 ± 2.82 , 83.88 ± 2.76 , and 96.25 ± 2.50 , respectively.

The IC₅₀ level for ABTS scavenging potential of saponins extracted from *C. neilgherrensis* and rutin were determined to be 41 µg/ml and 25 µg/ml, respectively (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Effect of saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* on the ABTS radical scavenging assay

The findings were depicted as a mean \pm SD of three independent assays. The results are statistically assessed by one-way ANOVA and Tukey's post hoc assay using SPSS software.

Effect of saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* on the reducing power assay

Figure 6 displayed the antioxidant properties of saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis*, which were compared to rutin utilized as standard. As the absorbance increases, it eventually demonstrates the reducing power. The saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* demonstrated a certain level of electron donation. The saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* exhibited a higher degree of Fe³⁺ reduction activity. The reference compound (rutin) exhibited a slightly greater reducing power compared to the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Effect of saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* on the reducing power assay

The findings were depicted as a mean \pm SD of three independent assays. The results are statistically assessed by one-way ANOVA and Tukey's post hoc assay using SPSS software.

Antimicrobial effects of the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis*

The effectiveness of the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* in inhibiting the pathogenic microorganisms such as *E. coli*, *B. subtilis*, *E. faecalis*, *S. aureus*, *S. pneumoniae*, *S. typhi*, *P. vulgaris*, *K. pneumoniae*, *C. albicans*, and *C. tropicalis*, was evaluated using the well diffusion technique, as depicted in Table 3 and Figure 7. The administration of various doses of the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* demonstrated remarkable antimicrobial efficacy against all the pathogens tested, similar to the results obtained with amoxicillin. The growth of various pathogens, particularly *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *M. luteus*, *E. coli*, and *P. vulgaris*, was significantly suppressed by the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* (Table 3).

The highest sensitivity to the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* was observed in *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *M. luteus*, *E. coli*, and *P. vulgaris*(Figure 7).

Table 3: Antimicrobial effects of the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis*

S. No	Microorganisms	Zone of Inhibition (MM)				
		100	75	50	25	+ve control
GRAM POSITIVE BACTERIA						
1	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	23	21	19	17	26
2	<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	19	17	15	13	24
3	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	21	19	16	14	25
4	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	20	18	14	12	24
5	<i>Micrococcus luteus</i>	22	20	17	15	25
GRAM NEGATIVE BACTERIA						
6	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	22	19	17	14	26
7	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	18	14	12	10	24
8	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	23	21	18	16	26
9	<i>Klebsiellapneumoniae</i>	20	17	15	12	25
10	<i>Shigelladysenteriae</i>	19	16	13	11	24
FUNGAL SPECIES						
9	<i>Candida albicans</i>	18	16	12	10	23
10	<i>Candida tropicalis</i>	16	14	11	09	22

Figure 7: Antimicrobial effects of the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis*

The treatment of different concentrations of the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* demonstrated effective antimicrobial activity against all the pathogens tested, similar to the results obtained with amoxicillin. The growth of various pathogens, particularly *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *M. luteus*, *E. coli*, and *P. vulgaris*, was significantly suppressed by the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis*.

Discussion

Saponins are a diverse class of naturally occurring plant-derived compounds that have gained more interests in the research because of their remarkable therapeutic potential. These fascinating molecules, found in a several plants, have been the subject of extensive research,

revealing their multifaceted biological activities and their promising applications in several areas, including medicine, agriculture, and industry [19]. Herbal plants have long been recognized as a good source of therapeutic compounds, and saponins are no exception. These plant-derived molecules demonstrate a broad spectrum of biological properties, like antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anticancer activities [20]. Interestingly, some plant species, such as the sapodilla plum, are known to contain a significant abundance of saponins and other valuable phytochemicals, including triterpenoids, Gallic acid, and flavonoids. These phytochemicals was known to demonstrate antimicrobial, spermicidal, anti-inflammatory, and analgesic properties, making them valuable agents to develop novel therapeutic agents [21].

The therapeutic potential of saponins has been extensively explored in recent years. These phytochemicals have demonstrated a remarkable array of biological activities, which have sparked the interest of researchers and the pharmaceutical industry [22]. One of the most prominent applications of saponins is their antimicrobial properties. Studies have shown that saponins can effectively inhibit the growth of various pathogenic microbes, making them potential agents to develop natural antimicrobial drugs [23]. Furthermore, saponins have been found to demonstrate anti-inflammatory and analgesic effects, which could be beneficial in the management of various inflammatory conditions and pain-related disorders [24]. Additionally, saponins have been investigated for their potential as antioxidants, which could be important to prevent and treat numerous age-related ailments [25]. As a result, the current work was executed to explore the phytochemical analysis, antimicrobial, and antioxidant properties of the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis*.

The preliminary physiochemical screening assays can be valuable in identifying the bioactive components, which can then contribute to the process of discovering and developing novel drugs. Additionally, these tests aid in the qualitative separation of

pharmacologically active chemical compounds. In this work, the qualitative analysis of the plant secondary metabolites were evaluated in the *C. neilgherrensis* root extracts, and the findings are shown in Table 1. There has been a recent surge in global interest and research on plants, particularly in their medical properties. This research has generated a substantial amount of evidence, highlighting the significant potential of medicinal plants in many traditional healing practices. Phytochemical screening has been conducted in numerous plants [26]. The significance of medicinal plants is in specific chemical compounds that elicit a distinct physiological response in the human body. The primary phytochemicals of utmost importance include alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, and phenolic compounds. Up to this point, over 10,000 phytochemicals have been discovered, although a significant portion of them are still unidentified. Medicinal plants include powerful phytochemical components that serve as significant sources of antibiotic compounds and contribute to their medicinal qualities [27]. The outcomes of the current work has proved the presence of various secondary metabolites in the aqueous, ethanolic, petroleum ether, and chloroform extracts of the *C. neilgherrensis*. The occurrence of the numerous phytochemicals like alkaloids, flavonoids, triterpenoids, carbohydrates, saponins, steroids, tannins, and Chlorogenic compounds were evidenced in the various solvent extracts of the *C. neilgherrensis*. When compared with chloroform and petroleum ether solvent extracts, the ethanolic and aqueous extracts of the *C. neilgherrensis* was demonstrated the occurrence of diverse phytochemicals.

Medicinal plants have long been recognized for their ability as a rich source of phytochemicals with potent antioxidant effects. These natural antioxidants play an essential role in counteracting free radicals and protecting cells from oxidative injury. Oxidative stress, caused by a disproportion between the free radical accumulation and antioxidant mechanisms, was participated in the onset of numerous diseases, including cancer, cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and aging [28]. The antioxidant capabilities of herbal plants

was widely explored, with researchers focusing on the ability of plant extracts to scavenge a variety of free radicals, such as DPPH, ABTS, H₂O₂, and NO. These studies have demonstrated that many medicinal plants are rich in compounds that can effectively neutralize these harmful reactive species, thereby offering potential therapeutic benefits. One of the major mechanisms by which medicinal plants demonstrate their antioxidant properties is via their high content of secondary metabolites. These phytochemicals have the capacity to donate hydrogen atoms or electrons, which can counteract free radicals and prevent them from causing cellular damage. The applications of plants as a source of natural antioxidants is well-recognized [29]. These plants offer a promising alternative to synthetic antioxidants, which can have potential side effects.

Free radicals are strongly connected to oxidative injury, while antioxidants act to reduce the oxidative damage to biological system. The presence of oxygen molecules can trigger the production of free radicals. These free radicals pose a significant threat since they can cause harm by reacting with vital biological components [30]. The free radicals interact with the antioxidants, ultimately neutralizing them before any damage occurs. Plants produce several secondary metabolites, many of which function as antioxidants [31]. Hence, the present investigation was executed to examine the in vitro free-radical scavenging capacity of saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis*. DPPH is a solid substance with a dark color and a crystalline structure, made up of molecules that are stable and have free radicals. Primarily, it serves as a pivotal technique to measure antioxidant capacity and is recognized as a prominent free radical. The DPPH radical exhibits a prominent violet hue when dissolved in a solution. However, it loses its color and turns either colorless or pale yellow when it is neutralized and transformed into DPPH-H [32]. Several plant extracts was documented to eliminate DPPH in laboratory conditions [33,34]. In this study, the saponins from the *C.*

neilgherrensis effectively eliminated DPPH radicals in a manner that was dependent on the concentration.

H₂O₂ radicals exhibit a high level of reactivity and have a less lifespan. They have the ability to cause harmful effects on crucial macromolecules [35]. The Haber-Weiss/Fenton reaction involves the production of hydroxyl radicals through the interaction of H₂O₂ with iron ions. The exceptional reactivity of H₂O₂ radicals results in significant harm to the cell, its components, and ultimately the entire organisms [36,37]. Hence, it is crucial to eliminate H₂O₂ radicals that induce harmful consequences. In the current work, the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* diminished the production of H₂O₂ radicals in dose-dependently. NO is a crucial cellular signaling molecule that plays a role in numerous physiological and pathological processes. It possesses potent vasodilatory properties and has a brief half-life of only a few seconds in the bloodstream [38]. The NO radical is harmful upon reacting with oxygen or superoxide anion radicals. In the present study, the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* successfully blocked the production of NO radicals. It has been found that various plant extracts and formulations are capable of scavenging NO radicals [39]. The ABTS^{•+} chromophore is generated via the interaction between ABTS and potassium persulfate, which transforms ABTS into its radical cation. The radical cation exhibits a blue hue and has the ability to absorb light at a wavelength of 734 nm. The ABTS^{•+} exhibits reactivity towards a wide range of antioxidants, such as phenols, thiols, and vitamin C [40]. In the current study, the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* demonstrated concentration-dependent suppression of ABTS radical generation. Previously, the *S. cumini* have also been found to provide a comparable effect [41].

Infectious diseases caused by pathogenic bacteria and fungi pose a significant problem to public health, especially with the growing concern of antimicrobial resistance. Medicinal plants have emerged as a promising source of natural antibiotics that can

potentially address this challenge [42]. The present work aims to study the antimicrobial capacity of the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* against several of common infectious pathogens, including *E. coli*, *B. subtilis*, *E. faecalis*, *S. aureus*, *S. pneumoniae*, *S. typhi*, *P. vulgaris*, *K. pneumoniae*, *C. albicans*, and *C. tropicalis*. It has been highlighted the potential of natural products in combating antibiotic resistant microorganisms. Herbal plants are rich in a diverse range of phytochemicals, which have demonstrated broad-spectrum of antimicrobial effects and the capacity to counteract resistance mechanisms [43]. Consequently, the need for potential antimicrobial candidates from plant-based sources has gained traction, as they offer a promising alternative to synthetic drugs and can serve as templates for the development of new antimicrobial agents [44]. The present study was carried out to screen the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* for its antimicrobial activity against the aforementioned pathogens. The findings are proved that the treatment of various doses of the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* demonstrated remarkable antimicrobial effects against the tested pathogens, similar to the results obtained with amoxicillin. The growth of various pathogens, particularly *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *M. luteus*, *E. coli*, and *P. vulgaris*, was significantly suppressed by the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis*.

Conclusion

The present investigation has evidenced the occurrence of numerous bioactive constituents in the extracts of *C. neilgherrensis* roots. The current findings further confirmed that the saponins extracted from the *C. neilgherrensis* roots have exhibited promising antibacterial and free radical scavenging properties. The current findings has revealed that the saponins from the *C. neilgherrensis* displays potent antioxidant and antibacterial characteristics, which could be advantageous in addressing disorders caused by infections and oxidative stress. Furthermore, additional research is required to ascertain the phytochemical

profile and specific molecular mechanisms by which *C. neilgherrensis* shows therapeutic effects.

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Figure legends